
CLUSTER AS A MEANS OF INCREASING INNOVATION IN THE REGION

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Abstract

The active application of the cluster approach aimed at increasing innovative activity will increase the competitiveness of domestic producers and accelerate the sustainable socio-economic development of the regions of Georgia. An analysis of domestic and foreign experience shows that the spread of clusters is one of the main characteristics of all highly developed economies. Efficient high-tech production is based on the integration of scientific, innovative, and manufacturing enterprises of various types.

Keywords: Cluster, innovation activity.

Introduction

According to M. Porter, a recognized authority on competition issues, in the modern economy, especially in the context of globalization, clusters come to the fore as a system of interconnections between forms and organizations, the significance of which as a whole exceeds the simple sum of its components [1].

The state program “Development of Science and Technology” for 2023-2030 noted the expediency of using such a tool as increasing the coordination of research activities in the country using the mechanism of technological platforms and innovative territorial clusters [3].

A cluster is a geographically concentrated group of interconnected enterprises that compete with each other, but at the same time work together, as well as organizations that support their activities, such as educational institutions, research centers, and trade enterprises [2].

Studies show that the use of clusters to the greatest extent implements the idea of sustainable development of the region [8].

The competitiveness and sustainable development of the region are interdependent and interdependent [6]. The problems of cluster development in the Georgian economy, taking into account the aspect of increasing the competitiveness of domestic producers, are developed in the works of many Georgian scientists. The factor of regionalization of international economic relations determines the creation of integration associations and transnational groupings [8].

Cluster solutions are also expedient for use in the agro-industrial complex, their creation, of course, along with other measures, improves the quality of life of the rural population, diversifies the economy, as well as an external effect - a reliable transport and social infrastructure. The creation of an integrated agro-industrial association on a regional scale is economically feasible. At the same time, it is advisable to have four high-risk and high-profit areas in a diversified association [267].

In the economy of the region, clusters are points of growth. A successfully functioning cluster-forming enterprise extends its influence to the immediate environment: suppliers of raw materials, materials, components, semi-finished products, and other counterparties. In turn, the efficiency of the environment has a positive impact on the further growth of the market power of the cluster-forming enterprise itself. As a result, the effect of the regional multiplier of the cluster is provided.

It should be noted that the sustainable development of the region has the opposite effect on clusters:

- their composition is changing – the share of innovatively active enterprises, and organizations providing pre-sales, after-sales services, and warranty services is increasing;

- master the best practices of infrastructure companies, financial institutions, educational institutions, and civil society organizations;

- links between cluster elements are strengthened;

- labor productivity increases at the enterprises included in the cluster.

Note that a cluster is a group of both geographically interconnected and mutually complementary organizations. Moreover, this set of organizations is distinguished by a high level of aggregation, therefore, in our opinion, the main advantage of the cluster mechanism is a complementary effect, which is expressed in an increase in labor productivity; development of small and medium business; accelerating the introduction of technological innovations; accumulation of a critical mass of human, innovative and production capital. This effect is enhanced with the help of organizations providing services for the storage, processing, and transmission of information, providing services related to the use of the Internet. The difference between the cluster of the economy of innovative development and the regional industrial complex is that first, the main integrating factors are virtual communication networks and new knowledge (innovation) that can maintain the

competitiveness of the cluster for a long time, and the internal integrator of the industrial complex are production facilities intended for the production of finished products.

An analysis of the literature made it possible to identify the following approaches to understanding the regional cluster:

- an institutional approach, from the point of view of which the basis of the cluster is not separate types of economic activity and not organizations, but institutions interacting within a certain geographical area;
- the functional approach, from the point of view of which the cluster is based on horizontal and vertical connections of the cluster members;
- integration approach, in which the cluster is based on integration links and unification processes, concentration, cooperation, and specialization of production;
- a strategic approach, within the framework of this approach, the cluster is a tool for implementing the development strategy;
- a systematic approach aimed at the optimal combination of strategic goals for the development of the state and business, allowing to take into account the influence of external macroeconomic factors;
- process approach. The cluster mechanism is considered a continuous and consistent implementation of a set of interrelated actions focused on the development of the business environment.

Foreign researchers of regional clusters use predominantly an institutional approach; in the works of Georgian authors, there is a structural component to a greater extent [6]. It should be noted that in practice there is a significant overlap and interconnectedness of approaches.

The cluster as a system includes:

- regulating and managing subsystems (legislative and executive authorities);
- support subsystem (banks and financial companies, educational and research institutes);
- service provision subsystem (suppliers of specialized services, infrastructure organizations, transport and communications organizations, etc.);
- supply subsystem (enterprises supplying raw materials, materials, semi-finished products, components, equipment, etc.);
- subsystem for the production of the final product.

The cluster approach focuses on the interconnection and interdependence of participants in the produc-

tion cycle for the creation of goods, services, and innovations. Clusters differ from other forms of cooperation in that the parties involved in a cluster are connected in a single chain and specialize in individual production activities or research.

The study of foreign experience shows that the formation of clusters can be considered one of the components of the sustainable development of the region. Efficient high-tech production is based on the integration of scientific, innovative, and manufacturing enterprises. As a result of the analysis of the foreign experience of clusters, the following models of cluster formation have been identified:

- 1) Italian;
- 2) Japanese;
- 3) Finnish;
- 4) North American;
- 5) Indian-Chinese.

According to the author, for use in our country, it is advisable to use elements of the Indian-Chinese model to a greater extent, in which the state plays a key role.

The objectives of the functioning of the cluster mechanism are to increase the economic, social, environmental, and institutional efficiency of the activities of the cluster members.

The cluster approach offers a new perspective on the development of the region, mainly based on horizontal links between firms, infrastructure facilities, research centers, public authorities, local governments, other participants, and symbiotic interdependence based on synergy. The cluster mechanism for managing the sustainable development of the region is shown in Figure 1.

The increase in social efficiency is manifested in the cluster in a more effective social policy by replenishing the regional budget, raising wages, and improving working conditions at the enterprises participating in the cluster.

Improving environmental efficiency in the cluster is to reduce the burden on the environment through the use of resource-saving, low-waste, and waste-free technologies.

The increase in institutional efficiency in the cluster is manifested in a more coordinated interaction of the actors of the region, which ensures the sustainable functioning of the socio-economic system of the region.

It should be noted that, even though innovation is stimulated by the horizontal struggle between competitors operating in the same markets, vertical relationships in the cluster between suppliers, main producers, and buyers are also important for the success of innovation.

Increasing economic efficiency in the cluster is manifested by:

Figure 1. Cluster Mechanism for Managing the Sustainable Development of the Region
Source: compiled by the author

- increase in the number of taxpayers and the taxable base of the region;
- increase labor productivity at the enterprises of the cluster;
- increase the potential of innovations;
- development of research and development infrastructure.

Cluster members become more competitive when entering international markets. The theoretical study made it possible to highlight the following advantages of the cluster approach in terms of ensuring the sustainable development of the region:

1) for the entire economy of the country as a whole and regions in particular, clusters play the role of growth points for the domestic market [2]. The high

competitiveness of the regional economy is based precisely on the strong positions of individual clusters. Regional clusters largely determine the level of economic development in the long run;

2) business processes are significantly optimized in the cluster, since cluster members can achieve the optimal scale of activity, and, thus, a high level of productivity and efficiency due to specialization;

3) the cluster approach allows the region to acquire properties that form a favorable environment for sustainable innovative development, characterized by a creative atmosphere of competition and partnership between cluster members;

4) the cluster approach is a means of achieving the goals of industrial policy (structural changes, increasing competitiveness, strengthening innovation,

etc.), an effective tool for stimulating regional development, which positively affects the improvement of the trade balance of the region. Employment, the level of average wages, and the competitiveness of the region's industry are also increasing [7];

5) the cluster form of organization of innovation activity creates a special form of innovation - the "aggregate innovative product" - the result of the activities of several organizations, which makes it possible to accelerate their distribution in the common regional economic space. At the same time, the processes of diversification of the region's economy are accelerating;

6) cluster policy in the agrarian sector, based on stimulating the formation and development of regional forms of territorial organization of production, also ensures the diversification development of the agro-industrial complex and improves the quality of life of the rural population. This takes into account the social, natural-climatic, and economic-geographical components of agricultural production [6];

7) the use of the cluster approach increases the complexity and consistency of the activities of the authorities of the region [9];

8) various types of synergy arise in the cluster [4].

9) The cluster approach is effective not only in the production sector but also in the types of economic activities associated with the formation, saving, and development of human potential.

Thus, the analysis of foreign experience shows the effectiveness of clusters in the modernization of the housing and communal sector - the most important factor in the formation of a comfortable living environment. In particular, based on the cluster mechanism, it is possible to solve the problem of the inflow of financial resources into the housing and communal sector and the radical renewal of funds.

The integration of education, science, and production in educational clusters makes it possible to provide significant external effects. Integration creates conditions for the development of an effective system of interaction between business and the labor market based on an increase in the opportunity to study best practices in the professional field. Business also benefits from cooperation, in particular, the competitiveness of the enterprise increases due to the training of personnel in advanced labor methods and technology transfer [3].

Undoubtedly, the creation of clusters in the healthcare sector is promising, since they can significantly improve the quality of medical and educational services, which is an important element in the quality of life of the population. As a result, the conditions for the formation, saving, and development of the human potential of Georgia are improving, as well as the competitiveness of the domestic healthcare and education systems, not only within the country but also in the world market. An analysis of the trends in the development of the healthcare management system allows us to conclude that the Georgian healthcare system, primarily at the regional level, already uses elements of cluster management.

Let us note the factors that positively influence the development of clusters in Georgia: the presence of significant theoretical developments and practical experience in organizing territorial production complexes; traditions of national education; high technological culture, etc.

Hinder the development of clusters:

- Lack of links between the scientific community and business structures;

- Poor quality of the investment climate;

- Low efficiency of functioning of associations and unions of entrepreneurs;

- Low level of trust between business, government, society, science, etc.

- Let's consider the prospects and possibilities of using the cluster mechanism in the regions of Georgia.

An important direction of the sustainable development of the regions is the accelerated innovative transformation of the territorial and spatial structure to improve the quality of life of the population and create favorable conditions for conducting financial and economic activities.

The problem of optimizing the spatial organization of the subjects of Georgia, overcoming the insufficient infrastructural provision of the region, and identifying support zones for development can be solved based on the formation of territories with a special economic regime and the use of a clustering mechanism.

The clustering mechanism will solve the following tasks:

- 1) to strengthen the framework of the settlement system based on increasing the connectivity of territories, using the unique competitive advantages of the multi-core structure of the region. The effect is achieved by optimizing the distribution of productive forces, efficient use of transport, communal and social infrastructure, spreading the diffusion of innovations to peripheral territories;

- 2) to form "growth poles" - territories with a special economic regime, by saturating the region's territory with mining and manufacturing facilities and the agro-industrial complex, ensuring an increase in employment of the population, as well as a redistribution of labor flows. These growth poles can accept significant investments and develop at an accelerated pace, ensuring economic growth and improving the quality of life of the population;

- 3) create a hierarchical network structure of roads that ensures the interaction of the transit network of highways of inter-municipal and local transport systems;

- 4) improve the quality and energy efficiency of engineering infrastructure.

- 5) It is advisable to solve these problems together with the implementation of the diversification of the economy, active support for innovation, using modern forms of support for innovative enterprises, and encouraging high-tech medium and small businesses.

"Development of economic sectors based on the cluster approach". In the region of Kvemo Kartli and

Imereti, metallurgical clusters are developing in Rustavi, Chiatura, and Zetafoni, a promising cluster in the gold and copper industries. Also in Imereti, it is very important to develop the machine-building cluster of Kutaisi, which provides for the re-profiling of unprofitable machine-building enterprises - now a technological platform and several technology parks have been created on the territory of the former machine-building plant.

- The development of the construction industry cluster in the regions of Adjara, Kakheti, Kvemo and Shida Kartli, Samegrelo, Tbilisi is necessary to further increase the volume of construction of new and reconstruction of existing housing.

- The strategy provides for the formation of agro-industrial clusters, which include the entire technological chain up to the production of the final product with a high share of value added. Such associations operate in the regions of Shida Kartli, Kvemo Kartli, Kakheti, Imereti, and others. The trading network of existing clusters is represented by 200 stores in these regions.

- The most promising are the clusters in the field of animal husbandry and the production of meat products, primarily in poultry (“Dila”, “Koda”, “Savaneti”, and others).

- Georgia has unique natural and climatic conditions for the development of tourism business in all regions of the country.

Three types of tourist clusters have already been created:

- Ski centers in Gudauri and Bakuriani, which have an international certificate of conformity);

- National parks (regions of Kakheti, Samegrelo, Imereti, Samtskhe-Javakheti), and Lagodekhi State Reserve;

- Specialized natural-landscape and historical-archaeological center “Sataplia“.

These cluster formations have significant potential for further growth and an increase in the export component. The territorial planning scheme provides for the creation of a transport and logistics cluster:

Tourist and recreational cluster based on the development of sports, ethnographic, religious, gastronomic, and ecological tourism, due to the multiplier effect, ensures the creation of new jobs. The tourism and recreation cluster, which provides opportunities for treatment, recreation, and medical tourism, can also become part of the regional healthcare development program in Georgia. As a result of the expansion of the tourism cluster, an international tourist and recreational hub will be formed, offering tourists several cultural, educational, extreme, adventure, ethnographic, health, hunting, fishing, recreational fishing, and sports tours. The expansion of the already-formed tourist cluster will improve the quality of life of the population.

Based on the results of the analysis of the problems of creating and functioning of clusters in the regions of Georgia, it can be concluded that it is expedient for the authorities to assist cluster members in the

implementation of complex technical re-equipment, as well as to support the foreign economic activity of cluster members, including the presentation of clusters on the international market.

It should be noted that such institutional structures for supporting clusters as cluster development centers have not been created in all regions of Georgia. Therefore, the experience of creating an infrastructure for the sustainable development of regions in the form of cluster development centers is very valuable for other regions of Georgia.

Conclusion

Thus, the study showed that the use of the cluster mechanism greatly contributes to the development of the regions of Georgia as a socio-economic system, to the greatest extent realizing the idea of innovative development of the territory. At the same time, state authorities at the central and regional levels and local governments should support the development of clusters, which are centers (points) of economic growth in the region, by:

- direct financial support for innovative projects;
- reducing the tax burden;
- ensuring the implementation of administrative procedures;
- provision of buildings and other infrastructure components;
- ensuring the transfer of information;
- ensuring transport links with other clusters or geographic areas;
- support in improving the reputation of the cluster;
- support in the development of business incubators and other forms and methods.

The following conclusions are of theoretical and practical significance:

1. When forming clusters in the regions of Georgia, several features should be taken into account: the geographical localization of the region, the state of the institutional and business environment, the commonality of products, resources, and technologies, the existing relationships between the cluster members;
2. Business entities participating in the cluster, seeking to increase their competitiveness in the market, increase their influence on such components of the marketing microenvironment as suppliers, consumers, and competitors. As a result, there is a shift in the boundaries of controlled and uncontrolled factors in the external environment of the organization. In turn, increasing the efficiency of counterparties has a positive impact on the further growth of the competitiveness of an economic entity.

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